

OP-DTT method

Materials: pipette (1-5 ml), micropipette (10-100 μ L), multichannel pipette (5-50 μ L), amber glass bottles (4 ml, 30 ml), reagent tanks, 96 well black plates with clear bottom.

Instrument: absorbance microplate reader (multiskan skyhigh each).

Reagent: dithiothreitol (DTT, CAS: 3483-12-3), 5,5-dithio-bis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid) (DTNB, CAS: 69-78-3), sodium dihydrogen phosphate monohydrate ($\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$), sodium phosphate dibasic (Na_2HPO_4), chelex, ultrapure water.

Preparation of solution:

-Prepare 0.05M phosphate buffer (PB, pH 7.4) by dissolving 5.2 g of Na_2HPO_4 and 1.697 g of $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 1 L of UP water. Treat PB with Chelex resin (batch method, 6.5 gChelex/L, 24h).

-Prepare 4 mM DTT solution by dissolving 0.016 g in 25 ml of PB.

-Prepare 0.4 mM DTT solution from 4 mM DTT solution. Dissolve 400 μ L of 4 mM DTT solution 3.6 mL of PB.

-Prepare 1.5 mM DTNB solution by dissolving 0.015 g in 25 ml PB.

Plate method:

1^oPreparation of the calibration curve (6 points: 50, 40, 30, 20, 10, 0 μ M DTT). Add different volumes of phosphate buffer (PB) to each calibration point (160, 165, 170, 175, 180, 185 μ L, see Figure 1). 2 replicates for each calibration point.

2^oAdd 160 μ L of each sample into the wells, 3 replicates for each sample (see Figure 1).

3^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C for 5 minutes.

4^oAdd different volumes of 0.4 mM DTT (25, 20, 15, 10, 5 μ L, and 0 μ L, see Figure 1) to each calibration point.

5^o Add 15 μ L of 1.5 mM DTNB to A row.

6^oAdd 25 μ L of 0.4 DTT to B-H row.

7^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C until after 10 minutes of reaction.

8^o Add 15 μ L of 1.5 mM DTNB to 1-3 columns (t=10min).

9^o Measure the TNB²⁻ absorbance of calibration curve (A row) at 412 nm at 37°C (t=0min).

10^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C until after 20 minutes of reaction.

11^o Add 15 µL of 1.5 mM DTNB to 4-6 columns (t=20min).

12^o Measure the TNB²⁻ absorbance of 1-3 columns at 412 nm at 37°C (t=10min).

13^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C until after 30 minutes of reaction.

14^o Add 15 µL of 1.5 mM DTNB to 7-9 columns (t=30min).

15^o Measure the TNB²⁻ absorbance of 4-6 columns at 412 nm at 37°C (t=20min).

16^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C until after 40 minutes of reaction.

17^o Add 15 µL of 1.5 mM DTNB to 10-12 columns (t=40min).

18^o Measure the TNB²⁻ absorbance of 7-9 columns at 412 nm at 37°C (t=30min).

19^o Incubate the microplate with high-speed agitation at 37°C for 10 minutes.

20^o Measure the TNB²⁻ absorbance of 10-12 columns at 412 nm at 37°C (t=40min).

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	160 μ L PB + 25 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB	165 μ L PB + 20 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB	170 μ L PB + 15 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB	175 μ L PB + 10 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB	180 μ L PB + 5 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB	185 μ L PB + 0 μ L DTT + 15 μ L DTNB						
B	SAMPLE 1 t=10 min		SAMPLE 1 t=20 min		SAMPLE 1 t=30 min		SAMPLE 1 t=40 min		SAMPLE 1			
C	SAMPLE 2 t=10 min		SAMPLE 2 t=20 min		SAMPLE 2 t=30 min		SAMPLE 2 t=40 min		SAMPLE 2			
D	SAMPLE 3 t=10 min		SAMPLE 3 t=20 min		SAMPLE 3 t=30 min		SAMPLE 3 t=40 min		SAMPLE 3			
E	SAMPLE 4 t=10 min		SAMPLE 4 t=20 min		SAMPLE 4 t=30 min		SAMPLE 4 t=40 min		SAMPLE 4			
F	SAMPLE 5 t=10 min		SAMPLE 5 t=20 min		SAMPLE 5 t=30 min		SAMPLE 5 t=40 min		SAMPLE 5			
G	SAMPLE 6 t=10 min		SAMPLE 6 t=20 min		SAMPLE 6 t=30 min		SAMPLE 6 t=40 min		SAMPLE 6			
H	SAMPLE 7 t=10 min		SAMPLE 7 t=20 min		SAMPLE 7 t=30 min		SAMPLE 7 t=40 min		SAMPLE 7			
	t=10min		t=20 min		t=30 min		t=40 min					

160 μ L sample +
 25 μ L DTT +
 15 μ L DTNB

Figure 1. Schematic representation of OP-DTT plate with the different reagents added to the different wells.